

Expansion of the Entangled Timelines Model: Accounting for General and Sophisticated Paradox Scenarios

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1 Introduction

General Relativity [1] developed by Albert Einstein, is a fundamental theory in physics that describes gravity as the curvature of space-time caused by the presence of matter and energy. This theory has been extensively confirmed through observations and experiments. However, despite its success, General Relativity raises certain aspects that still pose questions and challenges in theoretical physics. One of these aspects is the existence of spacetime geometries that exhibit closed timelike curves (CTCs), which would, in theory, allow for time travel. Nevertheless, it remains uncertain whether such geometries are

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permissible in our universe [3]. If they are, and time travel is possible, we will inevitably have paradoxes as a result [2, 5].

There are two main types of paradoxes, the first type is the **bootstrap paradox**, which is when something seems to be created from nothing, for example, imagine you're at home, and a older version of yourself suddenly appears and gives you the plans to build a time machine. So, you decide to follow the plans and embark on the task of constructing it. After several years of work, you finally manage to complete the time machine. Your first impulse is to use it to go back to the day you received the plans. You return to your home on that specific day and give the plans to your younger self. Then, it seems as if the plans came out of nowhere, as you received them from your future self and then gave them to your past self.

The second type of paradox is the **consistency paradox**, which is when something happens if and only if it doesn't happen. The most familiar example of this paradox is called the grandfather paradox. In this scenario, Alice, a time traveling physicist goes back in time because she wants to see her grandfather when he was young. However, this inadvertently leads to her grandfather not meeting his future wife (Alice's grandmother). As a result, Alice ceases to exist. But if Alice doesn't exist, she didn't travel back in time, and therefore, her grandfather did meet his wife, leading to Alice's existence. So, in this case, Alice is born if and only if she isn't born, illustrating the paradoxical nature of the situation.

These paradoxes are a serious problem that cannot be allowed in the universe, so we have to find a way to resolve them. We have different proposed resolutions to avoid it, the first one is the **Hawking Chronology Protection Conjecture** which is the conjecture that the universe does not allow time travel, then it is impossible. The **Novikov Self-Consistency Conjecture** suggests that we can never make any changes to the past, any attempts would inevitably fail, so if the past cannot be changed, then there is also no possibility of paradoxes. The **multiple-histories** (or **parallel-timelines**) suggest that when I back in time I exit into a different timeline, in which I can do whatever I want, without changing anything in the original timeline I came from, so there is no paradox.

In previous papers [3, 2, 5] we show the existence of time travel paradoxes that cannot be resolved by Novikov conjecture, however they can be resolved by multiple histories. This makes us think that the time travel necessarily implies multiple histories. But, what would be the mechanism of creation of the timelines? In the previous paper [4] was proposed a new model which resolved the paradox using parallel timelines and give a mechanism of creation of the timelines that is based on the many world interpretation of quantum mechanism, this model was called **Entangled timelines model (E-CTC)**, which we will describe in the next section.

2 Entangled Timelines Model

Before delving into the description of the model [4], let's first provide an overview of what the Many-Worlds Interpretation entails.

2.1 Many-Worlds Interpretation

According to the Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI), when dealing with a system that exhibits multiple possibilities, the universe undergoes a split into distinct branches. Each branch corresponds to a possible outcome. For instance, consider a particle in a superposition of spin-up and spin-down states. This implies that the particle has two potential measurement results. Additionally, imagine an observer who has not yet measured whether the particle is in a spin-up or spin-down state:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = (a|\text{Spin } \uparrow\rangle + b|\text{Spin } \downarrow\rangle) \otimes |\text{Observer}\rangle$$

Where a and b are arbitrary complex amplitudes such that $|a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1$. After the measurement, the system undergoes unitary evolution:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = a|\text{Spin } \uparrow\rangle \otimes |\text{Observer measured } \uparrow\rangle + b|\text{Spin } \downarrow\rangle \otimes |\text{Observer measured } \downarrow\rangle$$

At this point, the particle's state and observer's state become entangled, which we interpret as a branching, where now we have two version of the observer, one version measure spin up and the other version spin down. Each component of the wavefunction is a branch that represent a different world, so, when the observer interacts with the system, quantum entanglement occurs, and new worlds emerge.

2.2 The generic paradox

Now, let's explore the paradox model. In this model, we consider a time machine represented by the Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_{CTC} , where possible states are given by $|0\rangle$ (representing an empty time machine) and $|1\rangle$ (indicating a non-empty time machine). Additionally, we have an external system, denoted as \mathcal{H}_{ex} , with possible states represented by $|0\rangle$ (indicating that time travel will not occur) and $|1\rangle$ (indicating that time travel will occur). These Hilbert spaces encompass the potential quantum states of the systems.

The state of the overall system is the composite state of the time machine and the external system, denoted as $\mathcal{H}_{CTC} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{ex}$. The initial state is given by:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \tag{1}$$

This state signifies that the time machine is empty, and time travel will occur unless something prevents it. Since nothing has traveled back in time yet, no changes occur, and the same state persists at $t = 1$:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

However, as time travel occurs, the time machine is no longer empty at $t = 0$, leading to the state:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

This state represents a non-empty time machine and suggests that time travel will occur unless prevented. In order to create a paradox, we assume that if the time machine is not empty, time travel will be prevented. This results in the state:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle$$

However, since time travel does not occur, the time machine becomes empty again, returning to the state described in equation (1).

Herein lies a consistency paradox: time travel happens if and only if it doesn't. To resolve this paradox within the model, we must consider the concept of quantum superposition.

2.3 Resolve the paradox and mechanism for generating the timelines

As we observe, at $t = 0$, the time machine is in a superposition of being empty and non-empty. While the external system is not in superposition, as the initial condition always assumes time travel will occur, represented by $|1\rangle$, the overall state is as follows:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = (\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle) \otimes |1\rangle$$

where α and β are arbitrary complex amplitudes such that $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$. Expanding the tensor product reveals a separable state:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \tag{2}$$

Next, we apply the follow unitary evolution operator to transition from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$

$$u(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |x+y\rangle$$

Applying this operator to equation (2), we obtain

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \quad (3)$$

Now, we introduce another operator known as the timeline correlation operator, denoted as T , which describes time travel:

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = |y\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

When applying this operator to equation (3), we achieve the following:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \alpha|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \beta|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

Here, if the external system is in the state $|1\rangle$ at $t = 1$, indicating that time travel will occur, then at $t = 0$, the state of the time machine is $|1\rangle$, signifying that the time machine is not empty. Conversely, if the state of the external system at $t = 1$ is $|0\rangle$, implying that time travel will not occur, then at $t = 0$, the state of the time machine is $|0\rangle$, indicating that the time machine is empty. As we can see, comparing this to the initial state in equation (2), we have a consistent unitary evolution if $\alpha = \beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$.

Now, employing the Many-Worlds Interpretation in this time travel paradox model, we can discern that each term in the superposition represents a distinct timeline. In equation (2), the external system has not yet interacted with the time machine. Consequently, from the time machine perspective, there exist two timelines, however, from the standpoint of the external system, there is only one timeline since the systems are not yet entangled, and the timelines have not propagated.

In equation (3), at $t = 1$, the systems have interacted and become entangled. The observer from the external system will bifurcate into two versions: one who observes an empty time machine with no interaction and another version who observe a non-empty time machine with an interaction that prevented time travel. Now, time travel doesn't have to both happen and not happen simultaneously; it can simply occur in one timeline and not in the other.

3 Questions

Now, we are going to expand the entangled timeline model by exploring various scenarios:

3.1 Can the timelines be non-cyclic?

In the previous paper [4], an example involving Alice and a time-travel bomb was introduced. In this scenario, Alice in the first timeline sends a bomb to her past self at $t = 0$. Then, the bomb travels back in time to a new timeline, detonating and causing the demise of Alice of the second timeline. Consequently, Alice of the second timeline cannot send a bomb to the past because she is deceased. In the same previous paper, it was asserted that since Alice does not send the bomb, the time machine will be empty, and we return to the original timelines. This leads to cyclic timelines, which is necessary to maintain mathematical consistency.

One of the challenge addressed in this document is to discover a way for achieving non-cyclic timelines while preserving mathematical consistency. In this scenario, we can simply consider that since Alice is deceased, she will no longer send bombs back in time, making this the final timeline. Therefore, to achieve non-cyclic timelines, the last timeline must yield a zero result, signifying that Alice did not travel further into the past due to her demise. However, this condition presents a mathematical consistency problem because, at $t = 0$, we would encounter the absence of the state representing the first timeline.

Finding operators that allow us to obtain non-cyclic timelines while maintaining mathematical consistency and also have a logical physical interpretation poses a significant challenge. In the following, I will describe some of the attempts I have made to achieve this scenario of non-cyclical timelines.

3.1.1 First try

Let's consider the same Alice and the bomb example, then at $t = 0$ we have

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \quad (4)$$

Then, we use the same unitary evolution operator that in the basic model

$$u(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |x+y\rangle$$

and using this operator in the state $|\Psi(0)\rangle$ we have

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle$$

Now we operate the follow timelines correlation operator T

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + (1 - \delta_{0,y})|y\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

And we obtain

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

For n timelines, we would have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |i\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \\ |\Psi(1)\rangle &= u|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |i\rangle \otimes |i+1\rangle \\ |\Psi(0)\rangle &= T|\Psi(1)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |i+1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \right) \end{aligned}$$

As we can observe, we have mathematical consistency, as the overall state we obtain at $t = 0$ matches that of equation (4). However, from a physical perspective, it raises questions. Why, while being in one timeline, do we enter a superposition involving part of the first timeline and a new timeline? It doesn't make sense because if we were to jump back to the first timeline from any point where Alice has not died, we would inevitably encounter a paradox, and that is precisely what we want to avoid.

3.1.2 Second try

Another approach I attempted involved introducing an additional Hilbert space denoted as \mathcal{H}_h to describe the timeline number we are currently in. The possible quantum states of this system are $|0\rangle$ which represents the timeline null, and $|1\rangle$ represents the first timelines and so on. the composite Hilbert space would be $\mathcal{H}_h \otimes \mathcal{H}_{CTC} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{ex}$. Then, in this case the initial state at $t = 0$ is:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

Then, we use the next unitary evolution operator:

$$u(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |z\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |y+z\rangle$$

and using this operator in the state $|\Psi(0)\rangle$ we have:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle$$

Now, we operate the follow timelines correlation operator T in $|\Psi(1)\rangle$:

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |z\rangle) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + (1 - \delta_{0,z})|x+1\rangle \otimes |x+y\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

And we obtain:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle\right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle\right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

As we can observe, in this scenario, when we travel back in time from one timeline, we arrive at a superposition of a portion of the null timeline and a new timeline. However, the concept of arriving at a null timeline raises questions. What does it mean to arrive in a null timeline? Does it imply that we transition from one timeline to nothingness? This notion seems to suggest the destruction of the universe, which, doesn't make sense.

3.1.3 Third try

In this approach, I considered a particle in a superposition of existence, represented by $|1\rangle$, and non-existence, represented by $|0\rangle$. Then, the chain of events is described by the following table

Time	$h = 0$	$h = 1$
$t=0$	$ 0\rangle \otimes (0\rangle + 1\rangle)$	$ 1\rangle \otimes (0\rangle + 1\rangle)$
\downarrow	Nothing happens	Past and future particles annihilate or past particle only passes
$t=1$	$ 0\rangle \otimes (0\rangle + 1\rangle)$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle + 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle$
	Only in the time machine where a particle enters does time travel occur	Particle does not go into time machine and time travel does not occur

then at $t = 0$ tenemos:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right) + \beta|1\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right)$$

We apply the following evolution operator:

$$u = |0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes I + |1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes H$$

And we obtain the following overall state at $t = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(1)\rangle &= \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right) + \beta \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle\right) \\ &= \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right) + \beta|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Afterwards, the particle travels back in time to $t = 0$, and this is represented by the following timeline correlation operator T

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = (1 - \delta_{x,1})|y\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$$

and we obtain

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \right) + \alpha|1\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \right)$$

Comparing this with the initial state, we can see that we have a consistent unitary evolution if $\alpha = \beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$. As can be observed, when a particle does not enter the time machine in the first timeline, a superposition is obtained where a particle exists and does not exist, entering an empty time machine in the second timeline. However, these terms from the second timeline are not considered since they represent scenarios where the particle will never arrive. Only terms representing possible states where the particle can travel are taken into account.

However, with the correlation operator T , these terms from the superposition are also obtained, representing scenarios where nothing enters the time machine in the first timeline. These terms are part of the states in the second timeline, but since the particle will never travel there, they are not considered.

On the other hand, it can be observed that in the terms of the second timeline where the particle traveled, no particle entered the time machine in any of them. Therefore, time travel does not occur in those scenarios, and the process concludes.

3.2 Can we have an infinite number of timelines?

For this case, a variation of the scenario is introduced where the bombs are ineffective, and Alice attempts with more and more bombs to end her life, but Alice is immortal, and no matter how many bombs are sent, they are never sufficient to kill her.

This case, like the previous one, poses a challenge because to obtain infinite timelines, we need these timelines to be non-cyclic, meaning we never return to the first timeline. However, as we observed in the previous scenario, this leads to a mathematical inconsistency because at $t = 0$, we would have the absence of the state representing the first timeline. In the following, I will describe the attempts I made to obtain infinite timelines.

3.2.1 First try

In this case we have the following wavefunction at $t = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\frac{i+1}{2}}} |i\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Where the state of \mathcal{H}_{CTC} corresponds to the number of bombs inside the time machine, and the state of \mathcal{H}_{ex} corresponds to the number of bombs that Alice put inside the time machine. Alice starts always in the state $|1\rangle$ because she initially intends to send just one bomb.

Then using the usual unitary evolution operator u , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(1)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |3\rangle + \dots \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\frac{i+1}{2}}} |i\rangle \otimes |i+1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Next of this, we use the correlation operator T

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|y\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

and we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|3\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \dots \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\frac{i+2}{2}}} (|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |i+1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle) \end{aligned}$$

As we can observe, these operators provide mathematical consistency, but do they make sense from a physical perspective? It is noticeable that the probability amplitude decreases in each timeline. This could be attributed to the time machine operating with diminishing efficiency, resulting in a reduced probability of traveling to the past and creating a new timeline.

On the other hand, when using the correlation operator, we encounter a superposition of parts from the first timeline and the subsequent one. This might suggest that Alice always has the possibility to return to the first timeline, but such an outcome is not feasible, as it would lead to a paradox. Therefore, even though this solution maintains mathematical consistency, it doesn't work.

3.2.2 Second try

I also attempted to use the Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_h in this scenario, which denotes the number of the timeline we are in. The possible quantum states of this system is $|0\rangle$ which represents the timeline null, and $|1\rangle$ represents the first timelines and so on. the composite Hilbert space would be $\mathcal{H}_h \otimes \mathcal{H}_{CTC} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{ex}$. Then, in this case the initial state at $t = 0$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\frac{i+2}{2}}} |i+1\rangle \otimes |i\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Then, we use the next unitary evolution operator:

$$u(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |z\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |y+z\rangle$$

and using this operator in the state $|\Psi(0)\rangle$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(1)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \dots \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\frac{i+2}{2}}} |i+1\rangle \otimes |i\rangle \otimes |i+1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Now, we operate the follow timelines correlation operator T in $|\Psi(1)\rangle$:

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |z\rangle) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|x+1\rangle \otimes |z\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

And we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|3\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \dots \end{aligned}$$

As we can observe, in this scenario, we obtain again a probability of arrive from one timeline to a portion of the null timeline which seems to means the universe destructed.

3.3 What happens when more than one time machine is present?

Now, we will explore into the scenario involving two time machines. The illustration of the procedure considering this can be observed in the following diagram.

Figure 1: Illustration of the process considered in the case of two time machines.

In this scenario, two different approaches are tested.

3.3.1 First approach:

The first approach used to explore this case involved reusing the same time machine twice. The sequence of events considering this is given as follows:

Time	Timelines		
$t = -1$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$		
$t = 0$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	
$t = 1$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured by 1 bomb}\rangle$	
$t = 2$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured by 1 bomb}\rangle$	$ \text{2 Bombs}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured by 1 bomb}\rangle$
$t = 3$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured by 1 bomb}\rangle$	$ \text{2 Bombs}\rangle \otimes \text{Dead}\rangle$

where the states of the overall system will also be expressed as a tensor product in the composite Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_{CTC} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{ex}$. Now, let's put the values to the labels, where the state $|i\rangle$ of \mathcal{H}_{CTC} corresponds to i bombs inside the time machine ($|0\rangle$ means an empty time machine, as usual), and the state $|i\rangle$ of \mathcal{H}_{ex} corresponds to Alice putting i bombs inside the time machine, then if Alice is alive, she would send one bomb to the past, but if she is injured by i bombs, she would send $i+1$ bombs to the past. Then we have,

Time	Timelines		
$t = -1$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$		
$t = 0$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	
$t = 1$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	
$t = 2$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	$ 2\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$
$t = 3$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	$ 2\rangle \otimes 0\rangle$

The evolution operator that transports us from $t = -1$ to $t = 0$ is given by $B_1 = H \otimes I$, and the evolution operator that transport us from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$ is the usual $u_1(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |x+y\rangle$. For the correlation operator that represent the time travel from $t = 1$ to $t = 0$ would be giving by:

$$T_1(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = |x+y\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

where now $\dot{+}$ represents addition modulo 3. But finding an evolution operator that transports us from $t = 2$ to $t = 3$ is very tricky; in fact, I don't think that there exists a unitary operator that can do that. On the other hand, an operator that transports us from $t = 1$ to $t = 2$ has not been found yet, and I also suspect that this operator doesn't exist, sadly.

3.3.2 Second approach:

Another approach that was explored involves considering two distinct time machines. This entails introducing an additional Hilbert space that encompasses the possible quantum states of the second time machine. As a result, the overall state can be expressed as $\mathcal{H}_{CTC_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{CTC_2} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{ex}$ and the chain of events is described by the following table:

Time	Timelines		
$t = -1$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$		
$t = 0$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	
$t = 1$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured}\rangle$	
$t = 2$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured}\rangle$
$t = 3$	$ \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Alive}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Empty}\rangle \otimes \text{Injured}\rangle$	$ \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Bomb}\rangle \otimes \text{Dead}\rangle$

In this approach, the same values for the labels used in the previous approach will be considered.

Time	Timelines		
$t = -1$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$		
$t = 0$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	
$t = 1$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	
$t = 2$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$
$t = 3$	$ 0\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle$

So, we have that the state of the first time machine transitions from being empty to being in a superposition of two possible states, this is achieved by applying the follow bifurcation operator at $t = -1$

$$B_1 = H \otimes I \otimes I$$

Then, at $t = 0$, we have

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right) \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$$

Now, let's take into account the unitary evolution operator for n time machines, which describes the interaction between the external system and the time machine being used

$$u_i(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_n\rangle \otimes |x_{n+1}\rangle) = |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_n\rangle \otimes |x_i \dot{+} x_{n+1}\rangle \quad (5)$$

For the case of two time machines, we have:

$$u_i(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle) = |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_i + x_3\rangle \quad i \in \{1, 2\} \quad (6)$$

The evolution of the system when Alice is in the first time machine is described by the follow evolution operator:

$$u_1(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle) = |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_1 + x_3\rangle$$

Thus, we obtain the following state at $t = 1$:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle$$

Subsequently, the time travel takes place, and we transition to another timeline. This can be described by the timeline correlation operator T , which, for n time machines, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} T_i(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_n\rangle \otimes |x_{n+1}\rangle) &= \sum_{m=1}^i \delta_{m-1, x_{n+1}} \cdot \delta_{0, x_n} (|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_n\rangle \otimes |x_{n+1}\rangle) \\ &+ \delta_{x_i, 0} (\cdots \otimes |x_i + 1\rangle_i \otimes \cdots |i\rangle) + \delta_{x_i, 1} (\cdots \otimes |x_i - 1\rangle_i \otimes \cdots |i\rangle) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

For the case of two time machines, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} T_i(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle) &= \sum_{m=1}^i \delta_{m-1, x_3} \cdot \delta_{0, x_2} |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle \\ &+ \delta_{x_i, 0} (\cdots \otimes |x_i + 1\rangle_i \otimes \cdots |i\rangle) + \delta_{x_i, 1} (\cdots \otimes |x_i - 1\rangle_i \otimes \cdots |i\rangle) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

And for the time travel in the first time machine, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} T_1(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle) &= \delta_{0, x_3} \cdot \delta_{0, x_2} |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle \\ &+ \delta_{x_1, 0} (|x_1 + 1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle) + \delta_{x_1, 1} (|x_1 - 1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle) \end{aligned}$$

In the timeline where Alice was injured, she proceeds to the next time machine, which is in a superposition of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. The description of this process, will be given by the following bifurcation operator, which, for n time machines, is given by

$$B_i = \mathbf{I} \otimes \cdots \otimes \mathbf{I} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix}_{i-1, i} \otimes \mathbf{I} \otimes \cdots \otimes \mathbf{I}, \quad i \in \{2, \dots, n\} \quad (9)$$

where i represents the time machine through which Alice is passing. This operator applies the Hadamard gate to the target qubit only when the control qubit is in the state $|1\rangle$, and leaves it unchanged otherwise. The target qubit represents the time machine to which the external system is passing, and the control qubit represents the time machine before. In the case of two time machines, the target qubit is the second qubit, and the control qubit is the first qubit. In this scenario, the bifurcation operator B_2 is simply given by

$$B_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{I}$$

With the operator B_2 we obtain at $t = 2$ the following state:

$$|\Psi(2)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle$$

Now, we use the unitary evolution operator (6) to describe the system's evolution in the second time machine, as follows:

$$u_2(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle) = |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_2+x_3\rangle$$

Thus, we have:

$$|\Psi(3)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle$$

And to describe the next time travel we use (8) in the case of the time travel in the second time machine:

$$\begin{aligned} T_2(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle) &= \delta_{0,x_3} \cdot \delta_{0,x_2} |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle + \delta_{1,x_3} \cdot \delta_{0,x_2} |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes |x_3\rangle \\ &\quad + \delta_{x_2,0} (|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2+1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle) + \delta_{x_2,1} (|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2-1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle) \end{aligned}$$

and thus, we obtained $|\Psi(2)\rangle$. Successfully, we have derived the case for two time machines and, more generally, the scenario involving n time machines, considering the operators 5, 7, and 9.

3.4 What happens when a system in superposition goes into the time machine?

For this scenario, two distinct cases were examined:

3.4.1 Particle in a superposition of colors

For this scenario, we consider a toy model similar to the one presented in the paper [2]. In this model, we have a particle in a superposition of blue and green colors. To introduce time travel paradoxes in this model, we impose the following interactions between particles:

- If two particles with the same color interact, the incoming particle changes color.
- If two particles of different colors interact, they mutually annihilate each other.

For \mathcal{H}_{CTC} , we define, $|0\rangle = |\text{Empty}\rangle$, $|1\rangle = |\text{Blue Particle in the time M}\rangle$, $|2\rangle = |\text{Green Particle in the time M}\rangle$. For \mathcal{H}_{ex} , we define, $|0\rangle = |\text{Empty}\rangle$, $|1\rangle = |\text{Blue Particle}\rangle$, $|2\rangle = |\text{Green Particle}\rangle$. The chain of events is described by the following table

Time	h=0	h=1	...
t=0	$ 0\rangle \otimes (1\rangle + 2\rangle)$	$ 1\rangle \otimes (1\rangle + 2\rangle) + 2\rangle \otimes (1\rangle + 2\rangle)$...
↓	Nothing happens	Past and future particles collapse	...
t=1	$ 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle + 0\rangle \otimes 2\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle + 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle + 2\rangle \otimes 0\rangle + 2\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$...
	Particle goes into time machine	Superposition of particle going to the time machine and particle not going	...

We can see the more clearly the sequence of events in the figure 2.

The overall state at $t = 0$ is

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \alpha |0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \right) + \beta \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \right) \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \right) + \dots \\ |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Figure 2: Illustration of the process considered in the case of particle in superposition of colors.

To describe the time evolution from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$ we are going to consider the follow unitary evolution operator u

$$u(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |x\dot{+}y\rangle$$

Where $\dot{+}$ denotes addition modulo 3. Using this operator in $|\Psi(0)\rangle$, we obtain:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|2\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots$$

Then to describe the time travel, let's consider a timeline correlation operator T

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}\delta_{x,0}|y\rangle \otimes (|1\rangle + |2\rangle) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - \delta_{x,0})|y\rangle \otimes (|1\rangle + |2\rangle)$$

Applying this operator to $|\Psi(1)\rangle$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ &+ \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Comparing this with the equation (10), we can see that we have a consistent unitary evolution if $\alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, $\beta = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}$, $\gamma = \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}}$, \dots , $\alpha_{n+1} = \frac{\alpha_n}{\sqrt{2}}$, so we have

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \dots$$

Then, using the evolution operator u , we have:

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots$$

Next of this, we use the correlation operator T and we obtain

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \dots$$

3.4.2 Particle in superposition of existing and not existing

Now let's study the case where a particle is in a superposition of existence and non-existence. The chain of events is described by the following table:

Time	$h = 0$	$h = 1$
t=0	$ 0\rangle \otimes (0\rangle + 1\rangle)$	$ 1\rangle \otimes (0\rangle + 1\rangle)$
↓	Nothing happens	Past and future particles annihilate
t=1	$ 0\rangle \otimes (0\rangle + 1\rangle)$	$ 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle + 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle$
	Superposition of particle going to the time machine and particle not going	Particle does not go into time machine

In the following graphic, you can observe the process of events more clearly

Figure 3: Illustration of the process considered in the case of particle in superposition of existing and not existing.

So, we have the time machine in a superposition of being empty or containing a particle, and the external system is in a superposition of the particle existing or not existing. Therefore, at $t = 0$, we have the following state:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \right) + \beta|1\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \right)$$

We apply the following evolution operator:

$$u = |0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes I + |1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes H$$

And we obtain the following overall state at $t = 1$

$$|\Psi(1)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \right) + \beta \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \right) \\ = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \\ = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle$$

Now, let's consider the following timeline correlation operator T

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\delta_{x,0}|y\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle) + \delta_{x,1}|y\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle) \right)$$

and we obtain

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{\alpha}{2}|0\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle) + \frac{\alpha}{2}|1\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle) + \frac{\beta}{2}|0\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle) + \frac{\beta}{2}|0\rangle \otimes (|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$$

Comparing this with the initial state, we can see that we have a consistent unitary evolution if $\alpha = \beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$.

3.5 What happens when part of an entangled system goes into the time machine?

For this scenario, we will consider the same toy model used in the case of a particle in a superposition of colors, where the particle can be blue, represented by the state $|1\rangle$, or it can be green, represented by $|2\rangle$. However, in this case, we will take into account two particles whose colors are entangled in the form $(|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle)$. The following image illustrates the sequence of events

Figure 4: Illustration of the process considered in the case of entangled particle of colors

The chain of events for a particle from the system of two entangled particles entering the time machine is described in the following table

Time	$h=0$	$h=1$...
$t=0$	$ 0\rangle \otimes (1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle + 2\rangle \otimes 1\rangle)$	$(1\rangle + 2\rangle) \otimes (1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle + 2\rangle \otimes 1\rangle)$...
\downarrow	Nothing happens	Particles interact	...
$t=1$	$ 0\rangle \otimes (1\rangle \otimes 2\rangle + 2\rangle \otimes 1\rangle)$	$ 1\rangle \otimes (2\rangle \otimes 2\rangle + 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle) + 2\rangle \otimes (0\rangle \otimes 2\rangle + 1\rangle \otimes 1\rangle)$...
	Particle goes into time machine	Part of the entangled system going to the time machine and not going	...

Let's write the overall state at $t = 0$:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \right) + \beta \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \right) \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \right) + \dots \quad (11)$$

To describe the time evolution from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$ we are going to consider the follow unitary evolution operator u , that described the interaction between the particle entering the time machine and the time machine:

$$u(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle \otimes |z\rangle) = |x\rangle \otimes |x\dot{+}y\rangle \otimes |z\rangle$$

Where $\dot{+}$ denotes addition modulo 3. Applying this to $|\Psi(0)\rangle$ we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(1)\rangle &= \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2}|2\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta}{2}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Notice that the state of the particle entering the time machine has now become entangled with the state of the time machine. Next, time travel occurs and we can describe it using a timeline correlation operator T as follows:

$$T(|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}\delta_{x,0}|y\rangle \otimes (|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - \delta_{x,0})|y\rangle \otimes (|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle)$$

and we obtain the follows state at $t = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Comparing this with the equation (11), we can see that we have a consistent unitary evolution if $\alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, $\beta = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}$, $\gamma = \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}}$, \dots , $\alpha_{n+1} = \frac{\alpha_n}{\sqrt{2}}$, so we have

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \right) \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \right) + \dots$$

Then, using the evolution operator u , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(1)\rangle &= \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Next of this, we use the correlation operator T and we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(0)\rangle &= \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|2\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle \otimes |2\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \dots \end{aligned}$$

4 Discussion and future works

For the case of non-cyclic timelines, a mathematically consistent result was obtained. However, it lacks physical coherence. This is because, when interpreting the scenario where Alice, at $t = 1$, sends a bomb to the past at $t = 0$, and this bomb ends up in a superposition involving part from the first timeline and the subsequent timeline, the physical significance becomes unclear. The desired outcome is for objects sent to the past to arrive on a new timeline. However, despite achieving a mathematically consistent result, this is not what was obtained. One might contemplate the possibility of returning to the first timeline from a timeline where Alice has not died. However, this notion is fundamentally flawed, as it would inevitably lead to a paradox, precisely what we aim to avoid.

In a second attempt, a new Hilbert space representing the current timeline was added. Within this space, a null state was considered, symbolizing no place. This approach helps avoid the problem of causing a paradox. However, the transition still occurs from one timeline to a superposition of timelines. In this case, it is a superposition of part of a null timeline and the subsequent timeline. This seems to suggest a probability of reaching the null timeline. But what does it mean to transition from a timeline to a null timeline? This notion seems to imply that there is a probability of the universe being destroyed when time traveling, which is nonsensical.

On the other hand, in a third attempt, we considered a particle in a superposition of existence and non-existence. In this case, upon applying the timeline correlation operator T , we obtained the superposition of terms from the second timeline. However, terms representing the empty time machine were not considered. This is because the particle that traveled in time from the first timeline will not reach there; it can only reach the state $|1\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right)$. For this reason, this is the state representing the system at $t = 0$ in the second timeline. Additionally, it was observed that from the last timeline, we transitioned to zero, indicating that the process has concluded, and there are no more time travels.

In this case, considering certain conditions resulted in mathematical and physical consistency. However, I believe that in the second timeline, the state $|0\rangle \otimes \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle\right)$ should also be considered. This state is obtained when no particle enters the empty time machine from the first timeline. However, if it is considered, mathematical consistency is compromised. Therefore, it is still unclear how to achieve non-cyclic timelines without considering conditions such as only including states where the particle has traveled in time. It seems that to obtain a mathematically and physically consistent result, cyclic timelines may be necessary. For future work, one could attempt to find a meaningful physical interpretation for these equations or discover new operators to achieve both mathematical and physical consistency.

The case of infinite timelines is a non-cyclic scenario; therefore, the same mathematical consistency issue as in the previous case was encountered. This problem was addressed using operators similar to the ones in the previous case. However, the transition from one timeline to a superposition of the first and next timelines was once again observed, and its interpretation remains unclear. It seems to suggest a probability of returning to the first timeline, leading to a paradox. Considering the alternative solution with an additional Hilbert space implies a probability of universe destruction upon time travel, which is physically nonsensical. Despite achieving mathematically consistent results, the interpretation lacks meaning. Therefore, it seems impossible to have infinite timelines in a physically meaningful way. For future work, one could attempt to find a meaningful physical interpretation for these equations or discover new operators to achieve infinite timelines while maintaining mathematical and physical consistency.

For the case when more than one time machine is present, two options were considered. The first option was to reuse the same time machine, and in the presented case, it was reused twice. However, in this scenario, it was not possible to find unitary operators that transport us from $t = 1$ to $t = 2$ and from $t = 2$ to $t = 3$. Therefore, with this approach of reusing the same time machine multiple times, it was

not possible to obtain unitary operators that describe the process.

The second approach involved adding a Hilbert space for each time machine present. In this case, there were two time machines, so two Hilbert spaces were used to represent the two different time machines. With this setup, the evolution operator that transports us from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$ and from $t = 2$ to $t = 3$ was found, along with the correlation operator that takes us to the next timeline in the past for both time machines. Additionally, this approach also led to finding the unitary bifurcation operator B_2 , which transports us from $t = 1$ to $t = 2$. Thus, by representing each time machine with a different Hilbert space, the case of more than one time machine was successfully addressed, as it allowed the derivation of effective operators that can be generalized for n time machines.

For the case of a system in superposition entering a time machine, a toy model was considered where we have a particle in a superposition of being blue and green. Operators that well represent the interactions between particles were found. However, as we can observe, the probability amplitude is decreasing. This may be due to the fact that as the time machine is used, it becomes less effective and operates less efficiently. We can also observe that considering a particle in superposition entering the time machine results in infinite timelines, as there are always branches. However, this does not represent the case of infinite timelines discussed earlier because we still have a few timelines that are repeating, then it's not infinite timelines, it's still cyclic.

The case of part of an entangled system going to a time machine is very similar to the case of a particle in superposition entering the time machine. The difference is that in this case, we have the tensor product of three Hilbert spaces, where the first represents the time machine, the second represents the part of the external system that enters the time machine, and the third Hilbert space represents the part of the external system that did not enter. However, similar to the previous case, we obtain infinite timelines, where some are cyclic and return to the first.

In conclusion, some scenarios were successfully addressed, finding operators and mathematically consistent solutions. However, other cases presented challenges that still require further exploration and reflection to find satisfactory solutions. These results suggest the need to continue researching and developing new approaches to address outstanding issues in the fascinating field of time travel paradoxes.

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